

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Toolkit Content and Updates

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Executive Summary

This document presents the content and updates of the BioRural Toolkit, which will be the main tool developed by BioRural, presenting all the project results. The aim of the Toolkit is to provide access to the results and facilitate the use of information/knowledge collected and generated in the course of the project. It is also meant to enable interaction between rural actors, providing the platform to communicate, exchange experience and knowledge, and seek collaborations in the chosen fields of bioeconomy, thus supporting wider application of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

This document presents the update of technical description of the digital tool and the structure designed to provide access to its contents in an intuitive and user-friendly way, discusses the functionalities available to the registered and non-registered users, and proposes different methods for presentation of the content using suitable file formats for specific types of collected material. The main changes and updates done to the BioRural Toolkit since the publication of Deliverable 4.1 in M8 consist of changes in the following areas: 1.1 BioRural Toolkit Structure, 1.1.1 Factsheets, 1.1.2 Rural Bioeconomy inventories, 1.1.3 BioRural Success stories, and 1.1.5 Interactive Network Map.

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1.1 BioRural Toolkit Structure

The structure of BioRural Toolkit has been designed to fulfil the main purpose of this online tool – to provide access to the material collected in the course of the BioRural project implementation, through a user-friendly, intuitive interface, and to facilitate contact and collaboration of its users within the created networks. The toolkit can be found under the link <https://biorural-toolkit.eu/>.

The home page of the BioRural Toolkit consists of an interactive map showing the location of all the registered users, and the categories presenting the collected and generated material on bio-based solutions in an organized way (Figure 1). This layout corresponds with the main principle of the tool – to provide and facilitate the exchange of knowledge.

Figure 1. Screenshot of BioRural toolkit homepage

The layout presents the categories that correspond to those listed in WP4, T4.1 in a clear and explicit way, namely:

- (i) Factsheets of the rural Bioeconomy current status at national, regional and EU level → Factsheets
- (ii) An inventory of selected research results (papers and projects), commercial bio-based solutions and funding opportunities → Bioeconomy inventories
- (iii) The success stories' main characteristics combined with audio-visual material → BioRural success stories
- (iv) Knowledge sharing workshops recordings → Online tutorials
- (v) Outcomes of capacity building workshops in factsheets and audio-visual content → Capacity building workshops
- (vi) Practice abstracts
- (vii) Rural development blueprints → Business blueprints
- (viii) Policy and research guidelines → Policy and research

Each category can be entered by clicking on the specific tile, which directs the user to a separate page presenting the chosen content. The format of files included within each category and method of presentation of its contents has been adjusted to the specificity of the material. The file formats may include: Portable Document Format (PDF), Video file formats (MP4), text-based document formats (.doc, .docx, .xls, .ppt, .pptx), graphics (.jpg, .png), and other that may appear suitable in the course of data collection and preparation. All the above file formats have been chosen due to their widely accepted standards and widespread use among the Internet users.

1.1.1 Factsheets

The BioRural factsheets aim to provide detailed information on specific bioeconomy topics and their status in a quick and easily digestible way for all stakeholders. **For the creation of factsheets, input is initially drawn and populated from the results of T1.1 Current Bioeconomy Status in Europe (M1-M6)** [Leader: CERTH; Partners: All].

For ease of access, it was decided to divide the tile into three tabs: EU factsheets, National Factsheets, and Regional factsheets that will present area-specific content in the form of factsheets (PDF) available for downloading. The National Factsheets will consist of reports on bioeconomy status in all 14 project partner countries. The categorization into EU/National/Regional scope was included in the filtering options built in the search engine. Filtering will also be possible based on keywords provided by the user (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Filtering options of items presented in the Factsheets inventory

The Factsheets are prepared following a unified methodology and data presentation in order to facilitate the interpretation, analysis and comparison of the collected information. Each factsheet presents information arranged in three sections: an overview, details, and a gallery of images, and is possible to be downloaded in pdf format. An example of a factsheet in a pdf file format is presented in Annex I.

Registered users also have the option to upload their own bioeconomy factsheets to the platform using an online form presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Submission form for factsheets

All the submitted factsheets are visible to the author and the administrator of the Platform, who is responsible for screening the content before accepting it for publication. This process is described further in detail in section 1.1.2.

1.1.2 Rural Bioeconomy inventories

The BioRural inventory aims to provide stakeholders with an easily searchable database/repository of rural bioeconomy research results (papers and projects), commercial bio-based solutions and funding opportunities. In the toolkit, the Inventory has been divided into four main categories >Research Papers, Research projects, Commercial biobased solutions and Funding opportunities. The search engine allows also for filtering the items in the inventory based on the bioeconomy themes as well as keywords inserted by the user.

Figure 4. Filtering options based on the categories of bioeconomy inventories' items

The main input for this category will be provided from T4.2: BioRural Toolkit Development, Updates and Maintenance (M4-M36) [Leader: IUNG; Partners: All]. The specific input was requested from each project partner and is under the process of collection and uploading. The specific categories will consist of at least: 200 scientific papers, 50 research projects, 100 commercial bio-based solutions and 50 financing tools collected by the project partners and identified as relevant for the implementation of circular bio-based solutions in rural areas. Each of the collected items will be described using the information provided in the entry form, which will be adjusted to the specificity of a given category and, at the same time, allow for presenting all the solutions in a unified manner, e.g. containing visual materials, short description, contact information etc. Each solution will be assigned to specific bioeconomy sector/sectors and each will be provided a set of keywords, which will facilitate the search for a desirable solution in the inventories.

So far, the inventory consists of 129 items which have been submitted and accepted by the administrator. Specific numbers divided into categories are as follows: Factsheets: 2, Scientific_papers: 81, Research_projects: 19, Funding_opportunities: 7, Success_Stories: 1, Commercial_biobased_solutions: 19.

The submission form for each of the four categories of solutions is presented in Annex II.

All submitted files undergo a screening process performed by the administrator of the platform. After being submitted by registered users of the toolkit, all files have “private” status, which can be changed to “public” only be the toolkit administrator, who can view all files in the “admin panel” presented in Figure 5. The administrator screens the files for the relevance of information provided as well as makes sure they provide updated links to external information, such as project websites, journal websites, contact information and additional materials. For all of the information presented on the Platform, a source should be indicated.

Figure 5. Files submitted by registered toolkit users, visible in the "admin panel" section

After being accepted and published, the items collected in each category are presented as shown in Figure 6, each tile consisting of a picture, title and a category of presented solution: scientific paper/ research project/ commercial biobased solution/ financing tool. The search engine allows for searching through the collected items based on the keywords/bioeconomy themes/type of materials.

Figure 6. Collection of bio-based solutions including all four categories: scientific papers, research projects, commercial solutions, and financing tools

When choosing one of the displayed solutions, the user is presented with a page containing the information introduced in the designated submission form. The choice of information necessary to be provided for each of the categories of bio-based solutions was determined in a way as to allow for a uniform presentation of all items, regardless of their category. The universal layout for bio-based solutions’ is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Tab design for bioeconomy inventories.

Information is presented in a concise manner. On the left there is an image presenting the solution, a project logo, or the first page of a paper, and a short description below – depending on the type of the solution, it may be an abstract of a publication/project abstract or a short description in case of a commercial solution/financing tool. Information presented on the right is divided into three categories: (i) general information, e.g. keywords, bioeconomy theme, (ii) information on the solution provider/source with contact information and external links to

the publication/project/company website, and, optionally, (3) some additional materials which can be downloaded by the user. In case of scientific publications, no additional materials are expected.

1.1.3 BioRural Success stories

The input for this category will be provided by T2.4 Identification of success stories in each Rural Bioeconomy Platform (M10-M36) [Leader: ICO; Partners: All].

The BioRural success stories' main characteristics combined with audio-visual material will be presented in the toolkit. The aim of these is to provide an easily accessible overview of each success story, showcasing their innovations and factors that drove their development. The success stories are divided along the five bioeconomy themes: Food & agriculture, Forestry & natural habitat, Aquatic & water systems, Bioenergy, Biomaterials (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Tile presenting an example of success stories

At the launch of the toolkit, the 8 success stories that are included in BioRural and analysed in work package 2 will be available to all stakeholders. These consist of:

- Staramaki (Food & agriculture)
- Bio-based garden (Food & agriculture)
- SCIVEN (Forestry and natural habitats)
- Latvia's State Forests (Forestry and natural habitats)
- PUSTELNIA (Aquatic and water systems)
- ALGEN (Aquatic and water systems)
- ACEITES GUADALENTIN and BIOLIZA (Bioenergy)
- Natureplast (Biomaterials)

Each of the success stories will have a static page with the main information regarding the presented case: a photo and a short description on the left, and some general information and a video presenting the solution on the right, as it can be seen in the first uploaded success story - "Pustelnia" (Figure 9).

Pustelnia

PUSTELNIA farms two main species of fish: king carp and rainbow trout. In addition, catfish, pike, zander, tench, perch, grass carp and sturgeon are caught here. Carp production in this area dates back till 1760 and exists with minor changes till now. The production of trout and market of this species has been developing alongside for the last 20 years. Currently, the farm employs 25 workers. PUSTELNIA has a Fish Welfare Certificate for sustainable local aquaculture, and is inspected every year to obtain the Code of Good Fishing Practice Certificate. PUSTELNIA faced two main problems: it is located far from retail market (large retailers, processing plants) and the retail market, especially of carp, is unpredictable (extremely changing prices, seasonal sale). The idea was to create local, stable, all year round market for the species farmed there. We started from a small processing plant and supplying of the local restaurants in the range of 100 km. The regular delivery of fresh aquaculture products brought the idea of "Carp route"- 23 restaurants in the area serving dishes with local fish. This idea is being promoted in local media. Also many fish farms have developed at least seasonal local sale points of their fish or some form of fish gastronomy. In the last 3 years we developed PUSTELNIA shops (2 stationary shops and 2 mobile shops) and a fish restaurant. Since 2021 we are not selling our fish in wholesale anymore. We were inspired by numerous travels around Europe to find out how our speciality can be promoted in our local conditions.

Information

Contact Information
 Contact

Webpage
[Website](#)

Date founded
 1985

Funding sources
 private, public

Bioeconomy theme
 aquatic & water systems, food & agriculture

Why is it an innovative/circular bioeconomy success story:

- fishtruck
- in harmony in with nature
- maintaining the highest standards
- e-shop
- limiting food waste
- transitioning to renewable energy sources

Video

Pustelnia - hodowla ryb i restauracja

Do obejrze... Udostępnij

Obejrzyj w YouTube

Figure 9. Example of a static page presenting a success story of the Polish Fish Farm “Pustelnia”

Additional success stories will be added to the toolkit as the project progresses. These will come from the identification of success stories in Task 2.4. At the end of the project timeline, each theme will include at least 4 success stories. The audio-visual material produced by BioRural is limited to the 8 original success stories, however, if the newly identified projects/initiatives already have relevant audio-visual material, they will be included as well.

1.1.4 Online Knowledge Exchange Tutorials

(previously called: Workshop recordings)

Work package 3 (T.3.1 Online knowledge exchange on Bioeconomy (M1-M36) [Leader: UL; Partners: CERTH, AU, AlgEn, GGP, UC, IUNG, LLU, NP] will provide input for the inventory of the Online Knowledge Exchange Tutorials. A series of five EU online workshops with different groups of stakeholders and devoted to different bioeconomy themes will be organized and recorded with the aim to share and disseminate knowledge on bio-based solutions. Each workshop will be held over the course of 3 days covering lectures/discussions on ‘basic concept(s), technical principles,’ ‘showcase of good practices, factors of success’ and ‘cross-cutting themes.’ On each day, 5-6 lectures/discussions of around 15 minutes will be conducted. They will be recorded, and the recordings, along with

additional educational material, will be available to users categorized according to the bioeconomy themes (Figure 10):

- >Food & agriculture
- >Forestry and natural habitats
- >Aquatic and water systems
- >Bioenergy
- >Biomaterials

Figure 10. Online tutorials repository – videos will be divided into five categories corresponding to the themes of bioeconomy

At the moment, no recordings are available yet, since the workshops are to be conducted in the months 12-24. Each category presents information on the events planned to be organised, which can be downloaded in the pdf format by clicking on the “more information” button, visible on each tile in figure 10. Example of a document for downloading is presented in Annex III.

1.1.5 Interactive Network Map

The aim of the interactive network map is to provide an online space for bioeconomy stakeholders to register and be visible with the aim of facilitating cooperation and collaboration between rural bioeconomy stakeholders. Rural bioeconomy stakeholders identified in all tasks and work packages, in particular those identified in Task 2.1, have been invited to register on the toolkit and have the option to be visible on the interactive map. At least 400 stakeholders will be registered to the toolkit by the end of the project. At the moment, there are 294 registered users. The Interactive Network Map providing information about the registered stakeholders (Figure 11) is available to access from the homepage. Registered users/all users (TBD) will be able to search for a specific name/organization using the search engine (marked at the top of the map) or filter the stakeholders by type or bioeconomy theme (filtering options available below the map). The types declared by each registered stakeholder will be also visually differentiated using different pin colours for marking the location of stakeholders on the map.

The filtering/search results are available for downloading as .xls file (download button in the bottom right corner). They include the name and type of the stakeholder, bioeconomy theme, name and address of the institution and website address, if provided by the stakeholder.

Figure 11. Interactive map with its functionalities

The choice of stakeholder types comprises:

- Associations, clusters, NGOs
- Government and public administrations
- Private company/self-employed
- Research and education
- Other

The bioeconomy themes consist of:

- Aquatic/water systems
- Bioenergy
- Biomaterials

- Food/agriculture
- Forestry/natural habitats

Apart from the basic personal information a stakeholder will be required to provide in order to create an account (name, address, stakeholder type, bioeconomy theme), they will also have a possibility of adding a short description of their activities, organization, work focus etc., and providing contact information including a phone number and website address. The optional contact information consist also of social networks' profiles (Figure 12), which may facilitate creating collaboration networks, finding suitable partners for joint ventures or simply keeping up to date with the activities of other stakeholders in our area of interest.

Figure 12. Profile settings allowing for introduction of additional information such as social networks' profiles

Both the interactive map and the toolkit are accessible to non-registered users of the website. However, registration provides additional functionalities, such as storing files on the private account or adding files to the inventory (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Additional functionalities for registered users

Each registered user will be able to add items to the BioRural inventory using a designated online form. The suitable form containing questions relevant for the particular category of bio-based solution will appear upon selecting the category in the search tool. The process of adding files to specific categories as well as suitable forms used in each case are described in detail in section 1.1.2 Bioeconomy inventories.

All files submitted by the registered users will have the status of private files until accepted for publication by the administrator. Each user will be able to view and edit submitted files, as well as to check their publication status, as it is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Files submitted to the inventory by a registered user, each with a different publication status

All the users have also an opportunity to contribute to the development of the toolkit by reporting any problems with the website – a dedicated form has been prepared for this purpose, which is available under the “report a bug” button placed in the main menu (see Figure 15).

Figure 15. An option to report problems with the website is available in the main menu

1.1.6 Geoportal

The maps presented in 1.1.5 has been complemented with the Geoportal, which can be entered using the button in the top right corner. After opening the geoportal options, users can browse through different categories of geospatial information available for Europe to be displayed on the map. The information includes: (1) biodegradable municipal waste theoretical potential, (2) food waste theoretical potential, (3) forest theoretical potential, (4) manure theoretical potential, and (5) straw theoretical potential.

Figure 16. Geoportal presenting manure theoretical potential in Europe

1.1.7 Capacity building workshops

At the moment, there are no new materials to be presented in this category. A short notice has been displayed for users, informing about the content to be expected in 2024, as presented in Figure 17.

The aim of this section is to synthesize and provide key bioeconomy educational material originating out of the BioRural’s 42 national capacity building workshops. The input for this category will be provided by T3.2 Generation of interactive and multi-actor innovation at national level (M7-M24) [Leader; CERTH, Partners: All]. The tutorials will be divided into categories according to three thematic categories: (i) inland raw material production, (ii) aquatic raw material production and (iii) biological raw material processing. Each country will organise three workshops devoted to the above topics. The materials produced for the workshop participants as well as summary reports presenting the most valuable results, insights etc. in the form of factsheets or presentations (PDF) will be available for the registered/all users of the Toolkit (TBD).

Figure 17. Page presenting short description of the content to be expected in the category of capacity-building workshops

1.1.8 Practice abstracts

At the moment, a short notice is displayed, informing users about the content to be expected by April 2024 (Figure 18).

The inventory of practice abstracts will be fed with materials prepared by the project partners and divided into the five categories of bioeconomy themes. All the practice abstracts will be prepared in line with the EIP-AGRI common format.

Figure 18. Page presenting short description of the content to be expected in the category of practice abstracts

1.1.9 Business Blueprints

At the moment, a short notice is displayed, informing users about the content to be expected in 2025 (Figure 19). The inventory of Blueprints will offer business blueprints for rural development in each bioeconomy theme. The blueprints will be divided into categories according to bioeconomy themes.

Figure 19. Page presenting short description of the content to be expected in the category of business blueprints

1.1.10 Policy and research guidelines

The current page under this address informs about the content to be expected in 2025 (Figure 20).

The Policy and Research guidelines will be presented as drafted on Figure 20. **Error! Reference source not found.** The content for this page will be provided by T3.4 Policy guidelines for rural Bioeconomy development in M24-M36 [Leader: CERTH; Partners: All], therefore, the form of material presentation will be discussed and adjusted to the content produced. The policy guidelines will cover the following areas:

- Interactive and multi-actor innovation processes specific to bio-based solutions for rural areas;
- New funding formats enhancing innovation-driven research about bio-based solutions;
- Future research;
- Topics of interest for the national and EU research agendas (including further HE programming);
- Fostering a better targeted and shared research agenda on innovation-driven research and multi-actor projects.

Figure 20. Page presenting short description of the content to be expected in the category of policy and research guidelines

1.2 Plan for platform development

The plan for BioRural platform development takes into account the timeline of other work packages, which are to provide the content for the BioRural inventories. The BioRural Toolkit was launched operational for its users on as planned. As it was assumed, it did not offer all the above-mentioned functionalities at once. Figure 21 presents the timeline of the expected toolkit development. So far, the work has been conducted according to the schedule, however, thanks to the effort put into the realisation of WP4 by all partners involved, we have been able to start development of the bioeconomy inventory 6 months ahead of the schedule.

The remaining inventories and functionalities will be incorporated into the existing online tool in the course of the project, as well as the already existing inventories will be continuously updated with the material collected and generated in the other ongoing work packages.

Figure 21. BioRural toolkit development timeline

The toolkit is planned to be showcased during the workshops (T3.2, T3.3) and its functionalities are to be subject for evaluation of Bioeconomy actors, which will allow for improvement of the tool and development of additional features if necessary.

The BioRural Toolkit will be linked to the existing online bioeconomy tools, such as [Bioeconomy Platform](#), [AgEnergy Platform](#), and other online tools identified as relevant in this regard.

The BioRural Toolkit will remain operational as an open-access tool for at least three years after the end of the project.

2 Conclusions

This document has presented the content and updates of the BioRural Toolkit, considerable updates have been made to the BioRural Toolkit Structure, Factsheets, Rural Bioeconomy inventories, BioRural Success stories, and Interactive Network Map. In the coming months significant content updates will be achieved as partners will upload country specific factsheets, inventory, success stories and the outcomes of the knowledge exchange workshops.

BioRural toolkit will enable networking of stakeholders, knowledge sharing of bioeconomy as well as business models, and will support post-project sustainability.

In its current form and stage of development, it is ready to be an online repository of bio-based solutions that enables the interaction between rural actors and provides the ground for wider application of bio-based solutions in rural areas allowing the transitions of rural areas from linear economy to circular bio-based economy. It already offers a number of functionalities that enable bioeconomy knowledge sharing, in the form of national bioeconomy factsheets, inventories of scientific papers, projects, commercial solutions and financing tools, as well as success stories presenting examples of businesses successfully employing bio-solutions. They will be further complemented by new knowledge produced during the course of the project and other project results.

3 Annex

3.1 Annex I. – Factsheet on Greek Bioeconomy in the PDF file format

GREEK BIOECONOMY

Overview

The Greek Bioeconomy sector encompasses the food and agriculture sector, forestry, water, bioenergy and biomaterials sector employing 672,000 people and an added value of €12 billion.

-The main bioeconomy sector in Greece is the food and agriculture sector accounting for the majority of biomass supply (around 90%) and use (for food and feed) as well as employment and turnover. These are still largely dependent on linear production systems though increasing efforts are being made towards the sustainable use towards sustainable production.

-Greece has a large forestry area (6.6 million hectares) but represents a small portion of the bioeconomy and has the potential, if managed sustainably, to become a major supply of biomass and support for rural areas.

-In recent years the bioenergy and biomaterials sector have experienced rapid growth and these sectors are expected to grow rapidly as Greece transitions towards a low-carbon economic model.

-Key challenges for the development of a circular bioeconomy in Greece include changing demographics, infrastructure and long supply chains, access to funding for businesses, complex licensing procedures.

-Several policies have been developed in recent years that are supportive of the bioeconomy including the Greek Smart Specialization Strategy, The Greek National Strategy on Circular Economy, The Greek National Energy and Climate Action Plan for 2030 and the 2050 Roadmap

GREEK BIOECONOMY

Details

Policy and national strategies

The Greek Smart Specialization Strategy - national plan aimed at promoting research and innovation in Greece with an emphasis on the development of the bioeconomy (sustainable agriculture and forestry, advancing the use of renewable resources, and supporting the development of bio-based products and technologies).

[The Greek National Strategy on Circular Economy](#) - promotes the transition to a more sustainable and circular economy in Greece, in particular, the strategy emphasizes the importance of developing sustainable agricultural and forestry practices, as well as promoting the use of bio-based products and materials to support the circular and regenerative bioeconomy.

[The Greek National Energy and Climate Action Plan for 2030](#) and the 2050 Roadmap are comprehensive plans that aim to transition Greece towards a low-carbon economy. The plans identify the potential of biomass and biowaste as renewable energy sources, and include measures to promote the development of sustainable biomass production and use, as well as the circular use of biowaste.

Innovations and small scale- solutions

[Procos Sa](#), [Matric Pack](#), [PHEE](#), [Staramaki](#), [KIZI STUDIO](#), [PolyHealth S.A](#), [Coffeco](#), [BioCatPolymers](#), [BioSFera](#)

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GREEK BIOECONOMY

Gallery of pictures

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3.2 Annex II – Submission forms for bioeconomy inventories

3.2.1 Submission form for scientific papers

Page 1:

INFORMATION **PROVIDER/SOURCE** **MATERIAL**

Gallery of Pictures *
 Nie wybrano plików.

Title of the paper *

Short Description *

Provide keywords *

Bioeconomy theme

- food & agriculture
- forestry & natural habitat
- aquatic & water systems
- bioenergy
- biomaterials

Page 2:

INFORMATION	PROVIDER/SOURCE	MATERIAL
What is the name of the author *		
<input type="text"/>		
Journal *		
<input type="text"/>		
Official website/DOI *		
<input type="text"/>		
Contact information		
<input type="text"/>		
What is the date of publication *		
<input type="text"/>		
		<input type="button" value="PREVIOUS"/>
		<input type="button" value="NEXT"/>

Page 3:

INFORMATION	PROVIDER/SOURCE	MATERIAL
Provide audio-visual materials (image, video)		
<input type="text" value="links only"/>		
Provide additional materials (only open source)		
<input type="button" value="Przeglądaj..."/> Nie wybrano plików.		
		<input type="button" value="SEND"/>
		<input type="button" value="PREVIOUS"/>

3.2.2 Submission form for research projects

Page 1:

INFORMATION **PROVIDER/SOURCE** **MATERIAL**

Gallery of Pictures *
 Nie wybrano plików.

Title of the project *

Acronym

Short Description *

Provide keywords *

Bioeconomy theme

- food & agriculture
- forestry & natural habitat
- aquatic & water systems
- bioenergy
- biomaterials

Page 2:

INFORMATION	PROVIDER/SOURCE	MATERIAL
Funding Source		
<input type="text" value="national"/>		
Budget		
<input type="text"/>		
What is the name of the coordinator *		
<input type="text"/>		
Official website/DOI *		
<input type="text"/>		
Contact information		
<input type="text"/>		
What is the project duration? *		
<input type="text" value="14/09/2023 - 14/09/2023"/>		
		<input type="button" value="PREVIOUS"/>
		<input type="button" value="NEXT"/>

Page 3:

INFORMATION	PROVIDER/SOURCE	MATERIAL
Provide audio-visual materials (image, video)		
<input type="text" value="links only"/>		
Provide additional materials (only open source)		
<input type="button" value="Przeglądaj..."/> Nie wybrano plików.		
		<input type="button" value="SEND"/>
		<input type="button" value="PREVIOUS"/>

3.2.3 Submission form for commercial biobased solutions

Page 1:

INFORMATION **PROVIDER/SOURCE** **MATERIAL**

Gallery of Pictures *
[Przełączaj...](#) Nie wybrano plików.

Name of the solution *

Short Description *

Location *

Provide keywords *

Bioeconomy theme

- food & agriculture
- forestry & natural habitat
- aquatic & water systems
- bioenergy
- biomaterials

[NEXT](#)

Page 2:

INFORMATION **PROVIDER/SOURCE** **MATERIAL**

Funding Source

What is the name of the company *

Official website/DOI *

Contact form

[PREVIOUS](#) [NEXT](#)

Page 3:

INFORMATION **PROVIDER/SOURCE** **MATERIAL**

Provide audio-visual materials (image, video)

links only

Provide additional materials (only open source)

[Przeglądaj...](#) Nie wybrano plików.

[SEND](#)

[PREVIOUS](#)

3.2.4 Submission form for funding opportunities

Page 1:

INFORMATION **PROVIDER/SOURCE** **MATERIAL**

Gallery of Pictures *
 Nie wybrano plików.

Name of the financing tool *

Short Description *

Location *

Provide keywords *

Bioeconomy theme

- food & agriculture
- forestry & natural habitat
- aquatic & water systems
- bioenergy
- biomaterials

Page 2:

INFORMATION	PROVIDER/SOURCE	MATERIAL
Funding Source		
<input type="text" value="national"/>		
Type of funding		
<input type="text" value="direct payment"/>		
Budget		
<input type="text"/>		
What is the name of the financing institution? *		
<input type="text"/>		
Official website/DOI *		
<input type="text"/>		
Contact information		
<input type="text"/>		
What is the financing period *		
<input type="text" value="14/09/2023 - 14/09/2023"/>		
		<input type="button" value="PREVIOUS"/>
		<input type="button" value="NEXT"/>

Page 3:

INFORMATION	PROVIDER/SOURCE	MATERIAL
Provide audio-visual materials (image, video)		
<input type="text"/>		
Provide additional materials (only open source)		
<input type="button" value="Przeglądaj..."/> Nie wybrano plików.		
		<input type="button" value="SEND"/>
		<input type="button" value="PREVIOUS"/>

3.3 Annex III – Announcement of BioRural Knowledge Exchange Workshop on Aquatic Systems

Join us at the **BioRural Knowledge-exchange Workshop:
Advancing the European Rural Bioeconomy**

Aquatic Systems

**27 November –
1 December 2023
(tentative)**

Who should participate?

The BioRural Knowledge-exchange Workshop is designed for rural businesses, industry professionals, community leaders, policymakers and other actors sharing the passion and ambition of advancing rural bioeconomy. It provides a unique platform for networking, knowledge exchange, and collaboration.

Benefits of attending the workshop

By participating in this workshop, you will:

- Gain insights into the current state of the European rural Bioeconomy and its potential for growth and innovation;
- Discover success stories and best practices of bio-based solutions implemented in rural areas;
- Explore the BioRural Toolkit, an online open stakeholders' tool designed to facilitate information sharing and support decision-making processes;
- Engage in interactive discussions, workshops, and capacity-building sessions aimed at fostering regional development and the adoption of circular bio-based solutions;
- Contribute to the formation of the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) and help shape the future of sustainable rural communities.

Workshop Format

The BioRural Workshop will be held online over three consecutive days. Participants will have the opportunity to attend plenary sessions, interactive workshops, and virtual networking events. The schedule will feature engaging presentations by renowned experts, panel discussions, and case studies highlighting successful bio-based initiatives in rural areas.

Project Overview:

BioRural aims to establish a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network that fosters collaboration among stakeholders, promotes the adoption of bio-based solutions, and bridges the gap between cutting-edge innovations and everyday rural life. Through assessments, knowledge exchange, and the development of regional blueprints, BioRural strives to create a sustainable, inclusive, and circular Bioeconomy across Europe.

Save the Date and join us in shaping the future of rural communities through bio-based solutions!

For workshop updates and registration, please follow us on <https://biorural.eu>

Draft Programme

Day 1

11:00	Introduction to the workshop	<i>Maja Berden Zrimec (Algen)</i>
11:05	Overview presentation of Aquacultures and bioeconomy / circular economy	<i>Koushik Roy (Uni. South Bohemia, FROV)</i>
11:20	Status and perspective of algal systems in rural areas	<i>Robert Reinhardt & Maja Berden Zrimec (Algen)</i>
11:35	IMTA, a circulatory approach to aquaculture	<i>Erik Malta (CTAQUA)</i>
11:50	Microalgae related processes for nutrients recovery from wastes	<i>Gabriel Acien (University of Almeria)</i>
12:05	Microalgae-based biogas upgrading: a sustainability driven technology	<i>Raul Muñoz (University of Valladolid)</i>
12:20	Algae market and value chains	<i>Vitor Veldeho (EABA)</i>
12:35	Follow-up session: Q&A, moderated discussion with the presenters	<i>Moderator: Robert Reinhardt (Algen)</i>
12:55	Closure of Day 1	

Day 2		
11:00	Brief introduction of the Showcase Tour	<i>Maja Berden Zrimec (Algen)</i>
11:05	High sustainability aquafarming	<i>Irena Fonda (Fonda aquaculture)</i>
11:15	Sustainable local aquaculture by PUSTELNIA	<i>Anna Pać (Poland)</i>
11:25	Innovative and sustainable aquaculture solutions	<i>Katia Parati (Istituto Spallanzani)</i>
11:35	Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant - biorefinery valorisation of aquaculture biomass	<i>Tanya Meyer (BioBase Europe Pilot Plant)</i>
11:45	"Aquaculture in desert areas"	<i>Siggi Penno Winters (Arava)</i>
11:55	Microalgae as part of the circular economy	<i>Carole Llewellyn (Swansea University)</i>
12:05	Locality: "Nature-positive algae-based food, agriculture, aquaculture and textile products made in North and Baltic Sea ecosystems"	<i>Margarida Costa (Niva)</i>
12:15	ABG & CRONUS & FUELFORIA - using algae for wastewater treatment and biogenic CO2 conversion to biofuels	<i>Robert Reinhardt & Maja Berden Zrimec (Algen)</i>
12:25	Follow-up session: Q&A, moderated discussion with the presenters	<i>Moderator: Robert Reinhardt (Algen)</i>
12:55	Closure of Day 2	

Day 3		
11:00	Brief introduction of the Cross-cutting and emerging themes	<i>Maja Berden Zrimec (Algen)</i>
11:10	Opportunities for aquacultures in circular (bio)economy	<i>Ana Gavrilović (University of Zagreb)</i>
11:25	Sustainable agriculture: integration of algae in agricultural biomethane plants to produce biostimulants	<i>Elena Ficara (Politecnico di Milano)</i>
11:40	Policy for algal valorisation	<i>Silvio Mangini (Archimede)</i>
11:55	Innovation space BioBall - Promoting technologies for regional material use of biogenic by-products and waste streams	<i>Dorit Lehr & Jochen Michels (BioBall)</i>
12:10	Value Chain Generator for circular bioeconomy	<i>Jon Gorjup (VCG.ai)</i>
12:25	Clusters role in circular economy / CEE2ACT - Bioeconomy hubs	<i>Mateja Dermastia (Anteja)</i>
12:40	Follow-up session: Q&A, moderated discussion with the presenters	<i>Robert Reinhardt & Maja Berden Zrimec (Algen)</i>
12:55	Closure of workshop, evaluation & satisfaction survey	

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[blorural](https://www.linkedin.com/company/blorural)

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